

GENERAL CONCEPT OF CHRONIC TONZILLITIS.

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The relevance of the topic: Chronic tonsillitis, which is common in the field of otorhinolaryngology, is one of the most common diseases of the upper respiratory tract. Regarding the cause of the disease, according to various epidemiological data, this disease occurs in approximately 5-15% of the population, and in children up to 20-30%. This condition is one of the urgent problems encountered in medical practice. In scientific research conducted by foreign scientists Boris S. Preobrazhensky and Valentin T. Palchun, chronic tonsillitis was described as a prolonged infectious and allergic inflammation of the tonsils. The authors found that morphological changes in lymphoid tissue, the accumulation of microbial colonies in crypts, and immunological reactions are important in this disease.

Purpose of the work: the frequency of chronic tonsillitis in patients who applied to the Khorezm Regional Multidisciplinary Medical Center was studied.

The obtained results: during the study, 100 patients with chronic tonsillitis who applied to the Khorezm Regional Multidisciplinary Medical Center this year were studied. Out of 100 patients, 40 had an infectious form of chronic tonsillitis, and 60 had rheumatism as a complication of the infectious focus.

Conclusions: in conclusion, it can be said that chronic tonsillitis is an important otorhinolaryngological pathology that serves as a source of chronic infection in the human body. Early detection of the origin of the disease, the use of pathogenetically based treatment methods, and the improvement of preventive measures are of great importance in reducing the complications of the disease.

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